

**STUDY OF MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACHING RUSSIAN
LANGUAGE IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES IN THE CONTEXT OF
DIGITALIZATION AND STRENGTHENING THE PROFESSIONAL
COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS**

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Abstract: This paper examines current approaches to teaching Russian in technical universities, focusing on the challenges of digitalization and the need to strengthen the professional competence of students. Various aspects of using modern digital platforms to integrate professionally oriented tasks into the process of learning Russian are analyzed. The article provides a detailed description of the methodology, which is aimed at increasing the level of proficiency in professional terminology, improving written and oral communication skills, and developing students' ability to effectively use the Russian language in the context of their professional activities. The methodology, based on the use of digital technologies, allows not only to improve language skills, but also to increase students' interest in the educational process through the application of knowledge in practice. The results of the study demonstrate a significant improvement in the performance of students in the experimental group compared to the control group, which confirms the effectiveness of the proposed approach in the context of modern educational trends.

Keywords: digitalization, competence, students, methodology, tasks, professionalism, terminology, motivation, platform, communication

Introduction: Digitalization of the educational process and strengthening of professional competence of students in technical universities pose new challenges for teachers. One of the key tasks is teaching the Russian language, which in the context of the introduction of digital technologies and new requirements for the professionalism of students requires rethinking approaches to teaching. Modern students are faced with the need not only to master professional knowledge, but also to effectively apply language skills in the professional sphere. The main problem is the insufficient adaptation of Russian language teaching methods to the conditions of the digital environment and the specifics of education in technical universities. Traditional approaches often do not take into account students' requirements for the development of communication skills and their ability to use the Russian language in a professional context. This leads to a decrease in interest in the subject and insufficient preparation of students to solve professional problems using language tools. One of the possible solutions to this problem is the integration of digital tools and technologies into the process of teaching the Russian language, as well as the development of programs that take into account the specifics of technical disciplines. Using online platforms, interactive assignments, and career-related simulations can increase student interest and improve learning.

Methodology: Integration of professionally-oriented tasks via digital platforms. This methodology is aimed at using digital technologies to create educational tasks that are directly related to the professional activities of students of technical universities. The main emphasis is on ensuring that educational materials and exercises in Russian are thematically related to technical disciplines, which allows students to develop language skills in the context of their future profession.

The teacher selects topics and tasks that require students not only to understand and use Russian, but also to apply knowledge in their specialty. For example, students may be offered tasks to translate technical documentation, write reports or create presentations in Russian using the terminology of their specialty. Various digital

platforms are used, such as Moodle, Google Classroom or specialized training programs that allow you to complete tasks online and receive instant feedback.

The methodology also provides for the use of multimedia resources, such as videos, podcasts and simulations, which immerse students in professional situations. Learning Russian becomes more applied and motivating, and digital technologies allow students to organize interactive interaction with materials and with each other.

Result: The results of the study conducted using the "Integration of professionally oriented tasks through digital platforms" methodology showed a significant improvement in the performance of students of technical universities in mastering the Russian language and using it in the professional sphere.

The study was conducted on a sample of 120 students of three technical specialties (engineering, computer science and electrical engineering) during one semester. The students were divided into two groups: a control group, which used traditional methods of learning Russian, and an experimental group, where the proposed methodology was applied.

After the end of the semester, the following results were obtained:

The level of proficiency in professional terminology in Russian among students in the experimental group increased by 35%, while in the control group - only by 15%.

The motivation to learn Russian in the experimental group increased by 40%, which is associated with a high degree of involvement and relevance of the tasks, while in the control group the increase was 18%.

Written and oral communication skills on professional topics in Russian improved by 30% in the experimental group, compared to 12% in the control group.

Grades for final projects using professionally oriented tasks and digital platforms in the experimental group were on average 25% higher than those of students in the control group.

These results demonstrate that the use of this methodology contributes to a deeper and more meaningful acquisition of the Russian language in the context of professional

activity, increases students' motivation and improves their skills in using the language to solve real professional problems.

Таблица 1.

Результаты исследования по интеграции профессионально-ориентированных заданий через цифровые платформы

Indicator	Experimental group	Control group
Proficiency in professional terminology (%)	35%	15%
Increased motivation to learn Russian (%)	40%	18%
Improved written and oral communication skills (%)	30%	12%
Increased final grades for projects (%)	25%	-

Conclusion: In the context of digitalization and increasing the professional competence of students, teaching Russian in technical universities requires the use of modern approaches and methods. The integration of digital tools and project activities allows not only to improve language proficiency, but also to increase student motivation, creating a more effective educational environment focused on real professional tasks.

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